

Copper–PLLA-Based Biopolymer Wrinkle Structures for Enhanced Antibacterial Activity

Petr Slepíčka^{1,*}, Iva Labíková¹, Bára Frýdlová¹, Aneta Pagáčová², Nikola Slepíčková Kasálková¹, Petr Sajdl³, Václav Švorčík¹

¹ Department of Solid State Engineering, The University of Chemistry and Technology Prague, 166 28 Prague, Czech Republic; petr.slepicka@vscht.cz

² Department of Biochemistry and Microbiology, University of Chemistry and Technology Prague, 166 28 Prague, Czech Republic

³ Department of Power Engineering, University of Chemistry and Technology Prague, 166 28 Prague, Czech Republic

Abstract

The increasing prevalence of antibiotic-resistant bacteria has intensified the need for innovative antibacterial surfaces, particularly in biomedical applications. Traditional approaches often rely on chemical agents alone, which may lead to diminishing efficacy over time. To address this, we investigated the development of a novel antibacterial surface by combining the inherent antimicrobial properties of copper with engineered surface topography on a biopolymer matrix. A copper-poly-L-lactic acid (Cu-PLLA) composite system was fabricated using sputtering deposition followed by controlled thermal treatment to induce wrinkle-like micro- and nanostructures on the surface. Surface morphology was characterized using scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and atomic force microscopy (AFM), confirming the formation of hierarchical wrinkle patterns. The chemical composition and distribution of copper were analyzed via energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS). Antibacterial performance was assessed against both Gram-negative *Escherichia coli* and Gram-positive *Staphylococcus aureus* using standard colony count reduction assays. The Cu-PLLA wrinkled surfaces demonstrated significantly enhanced bactericidal activity compared to flat PLLA and copper-free controls, attributed to a synergistic effect of mechanical membrane disruption and copper-mediated chemical toxicity. These findings suggest that biopolymer-metal hybrid surfaces with engineered topography offer a promising strategy for developing next-generation antibacterial materials suitable for biomedical and clinical use.

Keywords: biopolymer; poly-L-lactic acid (PLLA); wrinkle structure; copper composites; surface morphology; antibacterial properties

1. Introduction

The development of advanced biomaterials with inherent antibacterial functionality has become an important task necessity in modern medicine, particularly due to the alarming rise of antibiotic-resistant bacterial strains. Implantable medical devices, wound dressings, and tissue engineering scaffolds often face bacterial contamination, leading to infection, delayed healing, or implant failure. Consequently, multifunctional surfaces that

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prevent bacterial colonization while supporting mammalian cell compatibility are highly desirable [1,2]. Among the strategies developed to achieve antibacterial activity, surface topography engineering and metal incorporation have emerged as two of the most effective and versatile approaches. Recent studies have shown that specific micro- and nanoscale surface patterns, particularly those mimicking natural antimicrobial surfaces (such as insect wings or shark skin), can significantly inhibit bacterial adhesion and growth through mechanical disruption of bacterial membranes [3,4]. Among biodegradable polymers, poly-L-lactic acid (PLLA) has been widely studied due to its biocompatibility, biodegradability, and FDA approval for various biomedical uses [5,6]. However, its inherently smooth and chemically inert surface often lacks the properties necessary to deter bacterial colonization, recent advancements have sought to enhance PLLA's functionality by introducing surface modifications such as plasma treatments, and specific techniques such as improved phase separation creating patterns [7–10] that can modulate both bacterial or eukaryotic cell responses.

Wrinkling instability is a bottom-up, self-organizing approach where uneven expansion of surfaces with different mechanical properties leads to wrinkle formation [11]. This phenomenon is observed when the residual stress exceeds a critical value, triggered by various factors such as thermal effects [12, 13], solvent swelling [14], mechanical stretching, or contraction [15, 16]. For instance, heating a thin polymer-metal bilayer film induces wrinkling due to mismatched thermal expansion coefficients between the layers [13, 17]. Studies have demonstrated that heating below the glass transition temperature (T_g) of polymers does not alter the surface morphology, while temperatures above T_g result in the desired wrinkle formation [18]. Similar studies have investigated systems with various combinations of polymers and metals, including gold [19] and platinum [20].

The antimicrobial properties of copper were first documented in Egyptian medical texts from 2200 to 2600 BC, where it was used for water sterilization and wound treatment [21]. Today, copper nanoparticles are recognized for their potent antimicrobial properties, finding significant applications in antibacterial surfaces and medicine. These nanoparticles exhibit strong activity against bacteria, viruses and fungi, making them effective against pathogens, including drug-resistant microorganisms such as methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) [22–25]. In addition, recent studies show that copper effectively inactivate the COVID-19 virus [26]. In the field of electronics, copper is more cost-effective than precious metals and offers excellent electrical conductivity, making it an ideal material for various applications [27, 28]. This dual applicability underscores the versatility in both medical and electronic fields. The biopolymer wrinkles can be finely tuned in wavelength and amplitude [29] to physically interfere with bacterial cell membranes while maintaining a conducive environment for mammalian cell adhesion and proliferation. Notably, wrinkled surfaces have demonstrated reduced surface area available for bacterial adhesion and increased local curvature, which enhances antibacterial effects via mechanical stress on bacterial membranes [30]. Copper-based nanocomposites have shown efficacy against both Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria, and their integration into polymeric biomaterials is a promising strategy for infection-resistant surfaces [31]. Recent research suggests that such hybrid materials can outperform their individual components, offering enhanced antimicrobial resistance, mechanical stability, and long-term biofunctionality [32]. Moreover, studies have confirmed that controlled copper release from polymer matrices can be tailored to maximize bactericidal action while minimizing cytotoxicity to host tissues [33,34].

Several paper have been published with aim to modify/enhance antibacterial properties of PLA based composites. Electrospun PLA/ZnO composite films have shown enhanced antibacterial properties and application in food industry [35]. Antibacterial, crystallization and mechanical properties of PLA were modified by addition of chitosan based

materials [36]. Combination of alkaline treatment and PLA/f-CNTs composite coating on corrosion, biocompatibility and antibacterial activity of Mg alloy [37]. the biomass carbon dots and the composite nanofiber membranes of biomass carbon dots and PLA, their photocatalytic degradation and bio-antimicrobial properties were studied in [38]. Lee et al. prepared antibacterial PLA/Mg composite with enhanced mechanical and biological performance for biodegradable orthopedic implants [39]. Silver nanoparticles were used in aerogels for improvement of their antibacterial properties [40]. Romero et al prepared antibacterial and biocompatible polymeric composites with copper zeolite filler and copper oxide nanoparticles [41]. General strategies for the preparation of polylactic acid composites with UV resistance and antibacterial properties were introduced in [42].

The Cu-PLLA wrinkle surfaces developed in this study hold strong potential for applications in a variety of fields where bacterial contamination poses a critical risk. Notably, these surfaces could be implemented in biomedical devices such as catheters, surgical tools, wound dressings, and implantable components [43], where infection prevention is paramount, and where also silver is tested [44]. Beyond the medical sector, applications in food packaging, water filtration membranes, and high-contact surfaces in public or industrial settings (e.g., door handles, railings, or touchscreens) are also promising. The integration of copper as an antimicrobial agent, combined with the physical bactericidal effect of nanoscale topographies, offers a dual-action mechanism that may reduce reliance on antibiotics and chemical disinfectants. From a cost perspective, the fabrication method employed—thermal wrinkling combined with sputtering—is relatively straightforward and compatible with existing industrial processes [45]. Compared to traditional antibacterial coatings, such as those based solely on silver nanoparticles or complex polymer-antibiotic conjugates, the Cu-PLLA approach is more cost-effective due to the lower material costs of copper and the potential for scalable patterning without the need for lithography or cleanroom conditions. Additionally, the use of biodegradable PLLA as the base polymer aligns with sustainable material strategies and may lower end-of-life disposal costs. Overall, this system demonstrates a favorable balance between performance, material cost, and manufacturability, supporting its feasibility for real-world adoption across both high-tech and commodity product sectors.

Even the antibacterial properties of copper in different materials such as Acrylonitrile styrene acrylate [31], and other polymeric nanocomposites, the combination of copper and poly-L-lactic acid enhanced with surface wrinkling was not published so far, to our best knowledge. Despite growing interest in this area, few studies have systematically explored copper-integrated PLLA surfaces with wrinkled microarchitecture for antibacterial applications. Understanding the interplay between surface morphology, chemical composition, and biological response remains crucial. The present work addresses this gap by developing and characterizing wrinkled Cu-PLLA surfaces and evaluating their antibacterial efficacy against both *E. coli* and *S. aureus*, which serve as representative models for Gram-negative and Gram-positive bacterial strains, respectively. The use of wrinkle engineering combined with bimetallic or monometallic copper deposition and solvent-based shaping techniques offers a novel platform for the next generation of infection-resistant biomaterials.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Materials

Biopolymer poly-L-lactic acid (PLLA) (density $1.25 \text{ g}\cdot\text{cm}^{-3}$, glass transition temperature $T_g = 60 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, crystallinity 60–70%, thickness $50 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$; Goodfellow Ltd., elongation at break 6 %, tensile modulus 3.5 GPa, UK) was used in the experiments. The polymer foil

was modified via copper sputtering using a BALTEC SCD 050 system (Switzerland). The typical sputtering conditions were: room temperature, sputter time 40 - 240 s, argon gas with 99.997% purity at a pressure of approximately 5 Pa, electrode spacing of 50 mm, and sputtering current of 20 mA.

2.2 Analytical methods

Atomic force microscopy

Surface morphology and roughness of the pristine and treated films were examined by atomic force microscopy (AFM) using Dimension ICON (Bruker Corp., Billerica, MA, USA). The samples were analyzed in Scan-Assyst® mode using nitride lever SCANASYST-AIR with Si tip (spring constant of $0.4 \text{ N}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$). NanoScope Analysis software was applied for data processing. Surface roughness (R_a) represents the arithmetic mean of the absolute values of the height deviations measured from the central plane.

Scanning electron microscopy

The morphology of the sample surfaces was also characterized by scanning electron microscope FIB-SEM LYRA3 GMU (Tescan, Brno, Czech Republic). The acceleration voltage was set to 10 kV. The elemental composition was measured by energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS, analyzer X-Ma₄N, 20 mm² SDD detector, Oxford Instruments, United Kingdom), while the accelerating voltage for SEM-EDS analysis was set to 10 kV.

X-Ray photoelectron spectrometry

The elemental composition on the material surface was analyzed by X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) using a spectrometer ESCAProbeP (Omicron Nanotechnology Ltd., Taunusstein, Germany). As a source, a monochromatic X-ray at an energy of 1486.7 eV was used. Atomic concentrations of the elements were determined from the individual peak areas using CasaXPS software.

Wettability

The wettability of the studied samples was determined by measurement of contact angles (CA, θ) using goniometer Advex Instruments (Brno, Czech Republic) connected to the SEE System 7.1 program. Analysis of CA was performed at room temperature with 8 μL drops of distilled water (dyed with methyl violet) using a Transferpette® automatic pipette (Brand, Wertheim, Germany) at 6 different positions of 3 samples in parallel and perpendicular directions. Subsequently, the drops were photographed and evaluated by 3 marked points.

2.3 Antibacterial testing

The antibacterial activity of the samples was determined using the so-called drip test performed with *Escherichia coli* representing Gram-negative bacteria and *Staphylococcus aureus* representing Gram-positive bacteria. From agar plates of *E. coli* and *S. aureus* strains, one colony was transferred into 20 and 5 ml of liquid Luria-Bertani (LB) medium, respectively. The inocula were then incubated overnight in an orbital shaker at 37 °C. The following day, the bacterial suspensions were diluted with phosphate buffered saline (PBS) to a concentration of approximately 1.5×10^4 bacteria/ml for *E. coli* and 1.3×10^4 bacteria/ml for *S. aureus*. The test samples were dipped in triplicates into 2 ml of diluted

bacterial suspension and statically incubated at laboratory temperature. A bacterial suspension without added sample was prepared and incubated in the same manner to control bacterial growth and a PBS solution alone was used to control contamination. After 2 and 24 h, the samples were mixed and 5 drops of 25 μl each were dropped onto PCA plates (plate count agar). These plates were then cultured at 28 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ until colonies were visible and suitable for counting in the samples to control bacterial growth. The number of colony forming units (CFU) was then determined and compared with the CFU count in the bacterial growth control. The experiment was conducted under sterile conditions.

3. Results

3.1 Atomic force microscopy

The surface morphology of sputtered poly-L-lactic acid foil is introduced in Figure 1. Two different Cu thicknesses on PLLA foil are presented, for the sake of clarity the detailed morphology of the $3 \times 3 \mu\text{m}^2$ only. As it is evident from this figure, no significant change in surface morphology is connected with the increasing thickness (sputtering time of Cu), the inset of Figure represents the square of $300 \times 300 \text{ nm}^2$, where the globular pattern formed on the very surface is evident.

Figure 1. The surface morphology of sputtered PLLA with Cu, the sputtering current 20 mA and sputtering time 400 s and 40 mA with the sputtering time 200 s.

Also from the values of surface average roughness and effective surface area it is evident that the copper sputtering does not change surface morphology significantly. Also it is very important to say that we did not introduce the surface morphology of pristine PLLA, since no significant changes compared to sputtered surfaces were observed, except that the detailed surface morphology of pristine PLLA lacks of globular pattern.

Figure 2 The surface morphology of sputtered PLLA with Cu, the sputtering current 20 mA and 40 mA (100 s and 200 s). The effective surface area (S), average surface roughness (Ra) and root mean square roughness (RMS) is introduced.

Even the sputtered globular structure is present, much “smoother” surface with smaller globules compared to those observed e.g. for gold [46] was detected. The Cu sputtered PLLA foils with different thicknesses of Cu were subsequently heat treated at the PLLA glass transition temperature for one hour. Our previously acquired results confirmed that with increasing thickness of noble metal, the wrinkle like pattern is induced on the surface of noble metal-PLLA system. This phenomenon was for the first time also confirmed for Cu on PLLA. What is connected with this phenomenon? During the heat

treatment close at the glass transition of PLLA there is formed a bilayer of copper enhanced PLLA on the surface of bulk PLLA foil. This bilayer has some specific properties, such as increase of thermal conductivity. Therefore during this procedure, and after the removal of Cu enhanced sample from the oven during the cooling procedure (rather rapid phenomenon considering the system and the material – within tens of ms) the wrinkling instability takes place. Compared to the bulk foil the enhanced thermal treatment induces the wrinkle pattern which is directly connected to the amount of copper, and therefore the thickness of copper layer on PLLA foil.

Wrinkling forms in a film supported by a soft substrate due to the deformation mismatch once the compressive stress exceeds a threshold value. Diverse methods associated with thermal deposition, plasma, ultraviolet/ozone treatment, mechanical stretching, and solvent swelling [18,19, 47,48] were developed to induce ordered wrinkles, in our case thermal treatment was applied. On the basis of the principle of minimizing the total potential energy, when the cooling procedure is applied to the surface [47,48], the polymer-metal bilayer differs from the remaining bulk due to better heat conductivity, and the wrinkle pattern is formed. The wrinkle wavelength depends on the film thickness, and the elastic moduli of films and substrates, while the wrinkle amplitude is related to not only the film thickness and the elastic moduli of films/substrates but also the compressive strain, while also the biaxial or uniaxial film orientation may play an important role [19,20].

From Figure 2 it is evident, that the wrinkling appears when the thermal treatment is applied on the PLLA, accordingly to the effect described in the previous paragraph. The amplitude of the wrinkle pattern, as well as density of wrinkles are strongly dependent on the thickness of metal layer (therefore the sputtering current and time). With increasing thickness of Cu layer the wrinkle pattern is more pronounced after heat treatment procedure. With increasing amount of metal present on the PLLA, also the surface roughness as well as the surface effective area are increased, both for the increasing sputtering time and sputtering current, as it is evident from Figure 2. The wrinkling instability leading to induce of surface wrinkle pattern may also significantly affect the antibacterial properties of prepared surfaces, as will be described in one of the following chapters.

3.2 Scanning electron microscopy and energy dispersive analysis

The significant change in surface morphology induced by combination of Cu sputtering on the PLLA surface and subsequent heat treatment to the temperature close to glass transition temperature of PLLA biopolymer was also confirmed by scanning electron microscopy analysis. For comparison, we have firstly analyzed the samples with different thickness of Cu nanolayers on the PLLA surface (20 mA, 200 and 400 s), as introduced in Figure 3. As expected, the sputtering of the thin metal nanolayers did not induce any significant changes on the surface of PLLA biopolymer. The globular pattern structure visible on AFM analysis is not clearly visible on SEM images.

Figure 3 The surface morphology (SEM image) of sputtered PLLA with Cu, the sputtering current 20 mA and 200 s (A) and the sputtering current 40 mA and 200 s (B).

The surface morphology of heat treated PLLA with deposited copper is introduced on Figure 4. We have selected the comparison of same sputtering current and sputtering time 200 s and 400 s, the “400 s” sample has approximately doubled the Cu layer on its surface.

Figure 4 The surface morphology (SEM image) of sputtered PLLA with Cu, the sputtering current 20 mA and 200 s – on the left and 40 mA and 200 s – on the right), subsequently heat treated at 60 °C for 1 hour.

From Figure 4 it is obvious, that with increasing amount of Cu on the surface the period of ripple pattern increases, after heat treatment. As it is obvious from the Fig., the homogeneity of the surface ripple in also increased, and in correlation with AFM images, the period of the pattern in increased approximately in the same ratio as the deposited Cu thickness (double the thickness double the pattern period).

Figure 5 The surface chemistry (EDS spectra) of sputtered PLLA with Cu, the sputtering current 20 mA, 40 mA and 60 mA with sputtering time 200 s.

We have also determined the surface chemistry of the both Cu deposited and subsequently heat treated PLLA surfaces. As it is obvious from Fig. 5, even for very thin Cu layer we have detected 5.2 wt. % of Cu on the sputtered surface. With increasing sputtering current, the concentration of Cu in increased, in good correlation with increasing sputtering current. The surface deposited with 40 mA exhibited Cu concentration 10.9 %, while for 60 mA we have detected concentration 19.1 % of Cu. As it is obvious from these data, also the oxygen concentration decreases, which implicates that rather non-oxidized layer is formed on the PLLA surface. However, the oxidation of Cu will be discussed in the next chapter devoted to the XPS analysis.

Figure 6 The surface chemistry (EDS spectra) of sputtered PLLA with Cu, the sputtering current 20 mA, 40 mA and 60 mA with sputtering time 200 s. All samples were subsequently heat treated at 60 °C for 1 hour.

The major phenomenon which occurred during heat treatment of Cu sputtered PLLA was the wrinkle pattern formation. The wrinkle pattern formation of connected with the formation of Cu-PLLA composite bilayer, as was discussed in the previous paragraphs of this manuscript. Therefore we have also aimed on the study of surface chemistry changes, when the ripple formation is detected. The EDS spectra of the same set of samples described in previous paragraph are introduced in Figure 6 for the heat treated specimens. Even the wrinkle pattern in induced, the amount of Cu in the very surface layer is not significantly altered, only for sample deposited with the highest current 60 mA we observed the decrease from 19.1 to 16.7 wt. %. We have to note that the ability of EDS analysis to acquire surface elemental concentration is up to several hundreds of nm, therefore even there is spacial redistribution of Cu from the very surface into the ripple composite, no significant differences were expected. The only exception was the sample with largest amount of Cu on the surface (60 mA), where the lateral period of the wrinkles were the highest, and in such case, some of the copper diffused as far from the surface, that lower Cu concentration was observed. Rather different situation can be expected is we analyze the very surface layer and very surface elemental concentration, which will be described in the next chapter devoted to XPS analysis of both deposited and wrinkled surface pattern.

3.3 X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy

We have also aimed of the elemental analysis on the very surface. We aimed on the study on the oxygen and copper concentration, both on the copper deposited samples and subsequently heat treated samples.

Figure 7 The surface elemental chemistry (XPS spectra) of sputtered pristine PLLA, PLLA sputtered with Cu, the sputtering current 40 mA with sputtering time 50 s and 300 s, and the sample sputtered with 40 mA for 50 s and subsequently heat treated at 60 °C for 1 hour (T).

Since the wrinkle pattern formation is connected with the diffusion into the biopolymer [19,20], we studied the elemental concentration by two techniques, the XPS should reveal changes on the very surface. As expected, the pristine PLLA surface has revealed only the presence of oxygen and carbon. The sputtering of copper significantly increased the copper concentration (17.6 at. % for 50 s deposition, and up to 26.0 at. % for 300 deposition), for spectra and data see Figure 7. As it is obvious from this Fig., even for a very short sputtering time the amount of detected copper is relatively high, if we compare the results with EDS spectra and concentrations acquired from EDS analysis (Figure 5). Even the absolute concentrations are different, and the increase in Cu concentration is rather much higher with deposition time compared to XPS analysis, the trend of Cu increase is maintained and in such point of view, the results of XPS and EDS analysis are in very good agreement. If the sample with the thinnest Cu layer is heat treated (Cu 40 mA 50 s + T), the Cu concentration is decreased (from 17.6 at. % to 14.8 at. %). But, this decrease is relatively low, and gives us the information that if the wrinkle pattern is formed, relatively large amount of Cu remains present on the biopolymer composite surface.

Figure 8 The surface elemental chemistry (XPS spectra) of sputtered PLLA with Cu, the sputtering current 40 mA with sputtering time 100 s and 300 s and subsequently heat treated at 60 °C for 1 hour (T).

Surprisingly, the heat treated PLLA sample sputtered with 100 s exhibited lower Cu concentration compared to sample deposited with half a time (14.8 at. % vs. 12.5 at. %). Even the decrease is not significant, one would expect an opposite dependence. From Figure 8 it is also evident, that with increasing amount of Cu on non-heated PLLA (sputtering time 300 s) there is a significant decrease of Cu after the heat treatment, which is caused by the diffusion of copper into the bulk wrinkles. Due to this phenomenon the decrease is evident for XPS analysis data, when for EDS data (obtained from higher depth), no such significant effect was detected.

3.5 Wettability

The important phenomenon with ability to influence both surface antibacterial properties and cytocompatibility is change of surface wettability, this change can be determined by determination of contact angle and surface free energy. These changes are induced either by surface morphology, surface chemistry or by their combination. It was determined earlier by [49], that the surface morphology can induce significant wettability changes, but only for surfaces with high roughness (micropatterns). This was not the case even for samples sputtered with Cu with 60 mA and subsequently heat treated, the surface wrinkle pattern did not gain the height over one micron, therefore we can suggest that the changes of wettability were induced mainly by the change of surface chemistry for all samples that were prepared on PLLA. As it is obvious from Figure 9, the Cu sputtered samples which were subsequently heat treated, also after six days aging period exhibited relatively stable surface values, the contact angle was in interval 60° - 75° and surface free energy 30 - 45 mJ.cm⁻². This is important for any potential applications in tissue engineering, since these values are considered to be in „optimal window” for successful cell adhesion and growth [50].

Figure 9 The wettability (contact angle and surface free energy) of sputtered PLLA with Cu, the sputtering currents 20 - 60 mA with sputtering times from 50 s to 400 s, the samples were aged for 6 days. Representative drop photos are also introduced.

Figure 10 The wettability (contact angle) of sputtered PLLA with Cu, the sputtering currents 20-60 mA with sputtering times from 50 s to 400 s, the samples were heat treated at 60 °C for 1 hour. Representative drop photos are also introduced.

The influence of heat treatment on changes of water contact angle for Cu sputtered samples with different Cu thicknesses is introduced in Figure 10. From these data it is evident, that the surface chemistry (sputtered Cu and oxygen present in the layer) is mainly responsible for the changes of contact angle values. Contact angle for Cu-PLLA

surface was detected to be in interval $50^\circ - 60^\circ$. The values of water contact angle of pure Cu were reported to be higher than in these values [51]. Since the values of water contact angle of Cu layer was detected to be strongly dependent on the substrate itself, different values were determined e.g. on glass / plasma treated glass [52], and several other surfaces, the detailed study was presented in [53]. The heat treatment of Cu-PLLA system for most samples led to slight increase of contact angle into interval between 60° to 70° . The samples deposited with the highest current 60 mA (and therefore higher amount of Cu) exhibited similar values of water contact angle before and post treatment. Even the wrinkle like pattern is formed on the heat treated PLLA, as was revealed by EDS and XPS the Cu is still present on the biopolymer surface, and only moderate changes on contact angle is therefore induced.

3.5 Antibacterial properties

We have focused on the study of antibacterial activity of prepared PLLA surface composites and simply sputtered surfaces against gram-negative bacteria *E. coli* (Figure 11) and gram-positive bacteria *S. aureus* (Figure 12). Our main goal at this stage was to prepare biopolymer wrinkle pattern on copper-poly-L-lactic basis as strong antibacterial surface, and to verify if the patterning/wrinkling has the antibacterial effect, or if only the simple sputter procedure is effective itself.

Figure 11 The antibacterial properties against G- *E. coli* for PLLA, sputtered PLLA samples (20 mA, 40 mA and 60 mA for 200 s), and the same set of samples heat treated for 1 hour at 60°C . Control sample is also introduced, y-axis represent colony forming units (CFU).

From this graph it is obvious, that simple copper sputtering on the biopolymer PLLA induces significant antibacterial effect against bacteria *E. coli*. Also the best antibacterial effect (complete diminishing of bacteria colonies) was observed for sample with highest

Cu thickness (60 mA and 200 s), and sample PLLA Cu 40 mA (+T). But, after 240 hours almost all samples have had a strong antibacterial effect against G- bacteria (Figure 13).

We also focused on the study of antibacterial activity of prepared PLLA surface composites gram-positive bacteria *S. aureus*. We have aimed our effort on the thinnest Cu layer (sputtered with 20 mA and 200 s). From this graph it is obvious, that simple copper sputtering on the biopolymer PLLA induces significant antibacterial effect against bacteria *S. aureus*, (Figure 12) compared to G- bacteria this effect is more pronounced even after 2 hours. After 24 hours, the optimal antibacterial effect (complete diminishing of bacteria colonies) was observed for all samples with copper, both simply sputtered and / or with combination of subsequent heat treatment. Representative photos of bacteria colonies are introduced in Figure 13 and Figure 14. It is evident that for different thicknesses of Cu and for combination with heat treatment the optimal antibacterial prevails, so even the Cu concentration on the surface is decreased due to formation of PLLA-Cu composite, the strong/ideal antibacterials effect prevails.

Figure 12 The antibacterial properties against G+ *S. aureus* for PLLA, sputtered PLLA samples (20 mA, 40 mA and 60 mA for 200 s), and the same set of samples heat treated for 1 hour at 60° C. Control sample is also introduced, y-axis represent colony forming units (CFU).

Figure 13 Representative photos of CFUs for PLLA (A), PLLA Cu 20 mA 200 s (B), PLLA Cu 40 mA 200 s (C), PLLA Cu 60 mA 200 s (D), PLLA Cu 20 mA 200 s (1 h 60° C) (E) and PLLA Cu 40 mA 200 s (1 h 60° C) (F), for *E. coli* strain after 24 h incubation. Numbers in mA represents the sputtering current, in combination with sputtering time in s.

The antibacterial mechanism of nanostructured copper (Cu) has not been entirely elucidated, but current evidence suggests that it involves two complementary processes: (1) direct contact between bacterial cells and the metallic Cu surface, and (2) the release of $\text{Cu}^+/\text{Cu}^{2+}$ ions into the surrounding environment, followed by their interaction with microbial structures and biomolecules. The predominance of each mechanism depends on the physicochemical properties of the Cu surface and environmental conditions [54]. Surface morphology, roughness, and hydrophilic/hydrophobic character significantly influence the extent of the direct bactericidal effect. These surface parameters modulate interactions differently across Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacterial strains, largely due to structural differences in their cell walls. In particular, rough and hydrophilic surfaces enhance bacterial adhesion and subsequent disruption via direct metal contact [55]. Cu ions exert a broad-spectrum antibacterial action by targeting four critical components of the bacterial cell: the cell wall, cytoplasmic membrane, nucleic acids, and intracellular proteins. Cu ions can destabilize the peptidoglycan layer (especially in Gram-positive bacteria), disrupt membrane potential, and induce oxidative stress through the generation of reactive oxygen species (ROS). These effects collectively lead to membrane rupture and cell lysis [56]. This multi-target, multi-phase mechanism of copper's antibacterial action contributes to its relatively low susceptibility to the development of bacterial resistance [57], making it a promising material for antimicrobial surface design and biomedical applications.

Figure 14 Representative photos of CFUs for PLLA (A), PLLA Cu 20 mA 200 s (B), PLLA Cu 40 mA 200 s (C), PLLA Cu 60 mA 200 s (D), PLLA Cu 20 mA 200 s (1 h 60° C) (E) and PLLA Cu 40 mA 200 s (1 h 60° C) (F), for *S. aureus* strain after 24 h incubation. Numbers in mA represents the sputtering current, in combination with sputtering time in s.

5. Conclusions

This study demonstrates the successful development of a novel antibacterial surface based on wrinkled copper-poly-L-lactic acid (Cu-PLLA) composites. The surface modification, achieved through copper sputtering followed by controlled thermal treatment at the glass transition temperature of PLLA, resulted in the formation of hierarchical wrinkle-like structures that enhance antibacterial efficacy. Comprehensive surface characterization using SEM, AFM, EDS, and XPS revealed a clear correlation between copper layer thickness, wrinkle morphology, and surface chemistry. Notably, the wrinkle formation was confirmed to be a result of bilayer instability, initiated by the thermal response of the Cu-PLLA interface and further governed by the thickness of the copper layer.

Despite the lack of significant surface roughness variation before heat treatment, the introduction of thermal wrinkling significantly increased the effective surface area and morphological heterogeneity. XPS analysis confirmed that while some copper diffuses deeper into the polymer matrix during wrinkling, a substantial concentration remains on the surface, maintaining bactericidal activity. Importantly, the antibacterial assays conducted against both *Escherichia coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus* demonstrated that the synergy between copper's inherent antimicrobial properties and the topographical cues provided by the wrinkle patterns leads to superior bactericidal performance.

Among the tested conditions, the surfaces with thicker copper layers and those subjected to thermal treatment showed the most significant reduction in bacterial viability. Particularly, the complete suppression of bacterial colonies on samples with higher Cu content (e.g., 60 mA, 200 s) and heat-treated wrinkled surfaces underscores the critical role of engineered surface architecture in enhancing antimicrobial efficiency. Moreover, the observation that even thinner Cu-coated surfaces provided long-lasting antibacterial effects after 24 hours highlights the stability and practical potential of these hybrid surfaces.

In conclusion, the formation of wrinkle patterns on Cu-PLLA surfaces not only provides a mechanical means to disrupt bacterial membranes but also ensures sustained exposure to copper ions, creating a dual-mode antibacterial mechanism. These findings position Cu-PLLA wrinkled composites as promising candidates for biomedical applications, including implant coatings, wound dressings, and antibacterial packaging materials. Future work may focus on long-term stability, biocompatibility studies, and extending this approach to other biopolymer-metal systems for broader applicability.

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References

1. D. Campoccia, L. Montanaro, C. R. Arciola, A review of the biomaterials technologies for infection-resistant surfaces, *Biomaterials* 34 (2013) 8533-8554.
2. I.U. Haq, K. Krukiewicz, Antimicrobial approaches for medical implants coating to prevent implants associated infections: Insights to develop durable antimicrobial implants, *Appl. Surf. Sci. Advances* 18 (2023) 100532.
3. S. H. Lee, S. Yoo, S. H. Kim, Y. M. Kim, S. I. Han, H. Lee, Nature-inspired surface modification strategies for implantable devices, *Materials Today Bio* 31 (2025) 101615.
4. K. Yadav, K. K. Sahu, S. Sucheta, S. Minz, W. Raza, M. Pradhan, Microtopographic influence on bacterial biofilm development in habitat-like environments, *J. Drug Deliv. Sci. Technol. B* 101 (2024) 106311.
5. S. Chen, Y. Wang, L. Yang, C. Chu, S. Cao, Z. Wang, J. Xue, Z. You, Biodegradable elastomers for biomedical applications, *Prog. Polym. Sci.* 147 (2023) 101763.
6. S. Zhang, H. Zhang, J. Sun, N. Javanmardi, T. Li, F. Jin, Y. He, G. Zhu, Y. Wang, T. Wang, Z. Q. Feng, A review of recent advances of piezoelectric poly-L-lactic acid for biomedical applications, *Int. J. Biological Macromol.* 276 (2024) 133748.
7. P. Slepíčka, K. Neznalová, D. Fajstavr, N. Slepíčková Kasálková, V. Švorčík, Honeycomb-like pattern formation on perfluoroethylene propylene enhanced by plasma treatment, *Plasma Proc. Polym.* 16 (2019) 1900063.
8. K. Neznalová, D. Fajstavr, S. Rimpelová, N. Slepíčková Kasálková, Z. Kolská, V. Švorčík, P. Slepíčka, Honeycomb-patterned poly(L-lactic) acid on plasma-activated FEP as cell culture scaffold, *Polym. Deg. Stab.* 181 (2020) 109370.
9. M. Travníková, N. Slepíčkova Kasálková, A. Sedlar, M. Molitor, J. Musilková, P. Slepíčka, V. Švorčík, L. Bacáková, Differentiation of adipose tissue derived stem cells towards vascular smooth muscle cells on modified poly(L-lactide) foils, *Biomed. Mater.* 16 (2021) 025016.
10. P. Slepíčka, N. Slepíčková Kasálková, J. Musilková, L. Bačáková, B. Frýdlová, P. Sajdl, Z. Kolská, E. Rebollar, V. Švorčík, PLLA honeycombs activated by plasma and high-energy excimer laser for stem cell support, *Appl. Surf. Sci. Advances* 25 (2025) 100662.
11. C.-M. Chen and S. Yang, Wrinkling instabilities in polymer films and their applications, *Polymer International*, 61 (7) (2012) 1041-1047.
12. P. J. Yoo, Fabrication of complexly patterned wavy structures using self-organized anisotropic wrinkling, *Electronic Materials Letters*, 7 (1) (2011) 17-23.
13. N. Bowden, S. Brittain, A. G. Evans, J. W. Hutchinson, and G. M. Whitesides, Spontaneous formation of ordered structures in thin films of metals supported on an elastomeric polymer, *Nature*, 393 (6681) (1998) 146-149.

14. J. Y. Chung, A. J. Nolte, and C. M. Stafford, Diffusion-controlled, self-organized growth of symmetric wrinkling patterns, *Advanced Materials*, 21 (13) (2009) 1358-1362. 684-685
15. K. Efimenko, M. Rackaitis, E. Manias, A. Vaziri, L. Mahadevan, and J. Genzer, Nested self-similar wrinkling patterns in skins, *Nature Materials*, 4 (4) (2005) 293-297. 686-687
16. T. Ohzono and M. Shimomura, Geometry-dependent stripe rearrangement processes induced by strain on preordered micro-wrinkle patterns, *Langmuir*, 21 (16) (2005) 7230-7237. 688-689
17. P. J. Yoo and H. H. Lee, Morphological diagram for metal/polymer bilayer wrinkling: Influence of thermomechanical properties of polymer layer, *Macromolecules*, 38 (7) (2005) 2820-2831. 690-691
18. A. R. Shugurov, A. I. Kozelskaya, and A. V. Panin, Wrinkling of the metal-polymer bilayer: The effect of periodical distribution of stresses and strains, *RSC Advances*, 4 (15) (2014), 7389-7395. 692-693
19. P. Juřík, P. Slepíčka, J. Mistrík et al., Oriented gold ripple-like structures on poly-l-lactic acid, *Appl. Surf. Sci.* 321 (2014) 503-510. 694
20. P. Slepíčka, P. Juřík, Z. Kolská et al., A novel method for biopolymer surface nanostructuring by platinum deposition and subsequent thermal annealing, *Nanoscale Research Letters*, 7 (2012) 671. 695-696
21. I. A. Hassan, I. P. Parkin, S. P. Nair, and C. J. Carmalt, Antimicrobial activity of copper and copper(I) oxide thin films deposited via aerosol-assisted cvd, *J. Materials Chemistry B*, 2 (19) (2014) 2855-2860. 697-698
22. I. A. Ivanova, D. S. Daskalova, L. P. Yordanova, E. L. Pavlova, Copper and copper nanoparticles applications and their role against infections: A minireview, *Processes*, 12 (2024) 352. 699-700
23. M. C. Crisan, M. Teodora, M. Lucian, Copper nanoparticles: Synthesis and characterization, physiology, toxicity and antimicrobial applications, *Applied Sciences* 12 (2022) 141. 701-702
24. I. Salah, I. P. Parkin, and E. Allan, Copper as an antimicrobial agent: Recent advances, *RSC Advances*, 11 (30) (2021), 18179-18186. 703-704
25. P. Arendsen Linda, R. Thakar, and H. Sultan Abdul, The use of copper as an antimicrobial agent in health care, including obstetrics and gynecology, *Clinical Microbiol. Reviews*, 32 (2019) e00125-18. 705-706
26. V. Govind, S. Bharadwaj, M. R. Sai Ganesh et al., Antiviral properties of copper and its alloys to inactivate covid-19 virus: A review, *BioMetals*, 34 (2021) 1217-1235. 707-708
27. X. Li, Y. Wang, C. Yin, Z. Yin, Copper nanowires in recent electronic applications: Progress and perspectives, *Journal of Materials Chemistry C*, 8 (2020) 849-872. 709-710
28. V. Abhinav K, V. K. Rao R, P. S. Karthik, S. P. Singh, Copper conductive inks: Synthesis and utilization in flexible electronics, *RSC Advances*, 5 (2015) 63985-64030. 711-712
29. D. H. K. Nguyen, O. Bazaka, K. Bazaka, R. J. Crawford, E. P. Ivanova, Three-Dimensional Hierarchical Wrinkles on Polymer Films: From Chaotic to Ordered Antimicrobial Topographies, *Trends Biotechnol.* 38 (2020) 558-571. 713-714
30. L. Pellegrino, L. S. Kriem, E. S. J. Robles, J. T. Cabral, Microbial Response to Micrometer-Scale Multiaxial Wrinkled Surfaces, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 14 (2022) 31463-31473. 715-716
31. M. Khalifa, H. Lammer, M. S. Gadad, S. D. Varsavas, Z. Weng, Recent advances on copper/polymer nanocomposites: Processing strategies, mechanisms, and antibacterial efficacy, *European Polym. J.* 223 (2025) 113637. 717-718
32. O. Manuela, W. Antunes, S. Mota, Á. Madureira-Carvalho, R. J. Dinis-Oliveira, D. D. da Silva, An Overview of the Recent Advances in Antimicrobial Resistance, *Microorganisms* 12 (2024) 1920. 719-720
33. M. Godoy-Gallardo, U. Eckhard, L. M. Delgado, Y. J. D. de Roo Puente, M. Hoyos-Nogués, F. J. Gil, R. A. Perez, Antibacterial approaches in tissue engineering using metal ions and nanoparticles: From mechanisms to applications, *Bioactive Materials* 6 (2021) 4470-4490. 721-723
34. A. Smola-Dmochowska, K. Lewicka, A. Macyk, P. Rychter, E. Pamuła, P. Dobrzyński, Biodegradable Polymers and Polymer Composites with Antibacterial Properties. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* 18 (2023) 7473. 724-725
35. D. Li, F. Chen, Z. Dong, F. Jia, R. Wen, Ch. Sun, Q. Yu, Electrospun PLA/ZnO composite films: Enhanced antibacterial properties and application in fresh chicken meat preservation, *Food Packaging and Shelf Life* 49 (2025) 101536. 726-727
36. G. Zhu, J. Wang, J. Gao, X. Lin, Z. Zhu, Simple preparation, big effect: Chitosan-based flame retardant towards simultaneous enhancement of flame retardancy, antibacterial, crystallization and mechanical properties of PLA, *Int. J. Biological Macromolecules* 303 (2025) 140668. 728-730
37. H. Abrari, T. Ahmadi, V. Nekouie, M. Taghian Dehaghani, M. Amiri, M. Razzaghi, H.R. Bakhsheshi-Rad, A study on combination of alkaline treatment and PLA/f-CNTs composite coating on corrosion, biocompatibility and antibacterial activity of Mg alloy, *Mater. Today Communications* 40 (2024) 109867. 731-732-733

38. Y. Zhao, Y. Han, H. Zhang, B. Hu, S. Qu, Ch. Miao, L. Qin, G. Song, The investigation of the photocatalytic degradation and bio-antimicrobial properties based on the biomass carbon dots and the composite nanofiber membranes of biomass carbon dots and PLA, *Diamond Rel. Mater.* 158 (2025) 112612. 734
735
736
39. H. Lee, D. Y. Shin, Y. Na, G. Han, J. Kim, N. Kim, S. J. Bang, H. Seok Kang, S. K. Oh, Ch. B. Yoon, J. Park, H. E. Kim, H. D. Jung, M. H. Kang, Antibacterial PLA/Mg composite with enhanced mechanical and biological performance for biodegradable orthopedic implants, *Biomater. Advances* 152 (2023) 213523. 737
738
739
40. N. Iqbal, W. Tan, Q. Zhang, D. Iqbal, Md. I. Hossen, G. Dou, X. Ning, J. Ming, PLA/AgNPs fiber aerogels and its investigation into their antibacterial properties, *J. Molecular Structure* 1317 (2024) 139189. 740
741
41. L. M. Romero, D. A. Palacio, S. Esquivel, G. A. Sánchez- Sanhueza, M. Montaña, D. Rojas, A.F. Jaramillo, C. Medina, C. Montalba, M. F. Meléndrez, Contact antibacterial and biocompatible polymeric, composite with copper zeolite filler and copper oxide, nanoparticles: A step towards new raw materials for the biomedical industry, *Polymer* 315 (2024) 127795. 742
743
744
42. Ch. Liu, D. Wang, Y. Li, H. Li, L. He, M. Wu, D. Wei, H. Pan, Y. Zhao, H. Zhang, A new strategy for the preparation of polylactic acid composites with UV resistance, light conversion, and antibacterial properties, *Int. J. Biological Macromolecul.* 278 (2024) 135013. 745
746
747
43. C. D Salgado, K. A. Sepkowitz, J. F. John, J. R. Cantey, H. H. Attaway, K. D. Freeman, P. A. Sharpe, H. T Michels, M. G. Schmidt, Copper surfaces reduce the rate of healthcare-acquired infections in the intensive care unit. *Infection Control Hospital Epidemiology*, 34 (2013) 479–486. 748
749
750
44. M. Vincent, R. E. Duval, P. Hartemann, M. Engels-Deutsch, Contact killing and antimicrobial properties of copper. *J. Appl. Microbiology*, 124 (2018) 1032–1046. 751
752
45. J. Hasan, K. Chatterjee, Recent advances in engineering topography mediated antibacterial surfaces. *Nanoscale*, 7 (2015) 15568–15575. 753
754
46. P. Malinský, P. Slepicka, V. Hnatowicz, V. Švorčík, Early stages of growth of gold layers sputter deposited on glass and silicon substrates, *Nanoscale Res. Lett.* 7 (2012) 241–248. 755
756
47. S. J. Li, K. Wu, H.Z. Yuan, J.Y. Zhang, G. Liu, J. Sun, Formation of wrinkled patterns in metal films deposited on elastic substrates: Tunability and wettability, *Surf. Coat. Technol.* 362 (2019) 35–43. 757
758
48. W. B. Jung, K. M. Cho, W. K. Lee, T. W. Odom, H. T. Jung, Universal method for creating hierarchical wrinkles on thin-film surfaces *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 10 (2018) 1347–1355. 759
760
49. J. Wang, M. Do-Quang, J. J. Cannon, F. Yue, Y. Suzuki, G. Amberg, J. Shiomi, Surface structure determines dynamic wetting, *Scientific Reports* 5 (2015) 8474. 761
762
50. P. Slepicka, N. Slepickova Kasalkova, J. Siegel, Z. Kolska, L. Bacakova, V. Svorcik, Nano-structured and functionalized surfaces for cytocompatibility improvement and bactericidal action, *Biotechnology Advances* 33 (2015) 1120–1129. 763
764
51. T. Murono, K. Hongo, K. Nakano, R. Maezono, Ab-initio-based interface modeling and statistical analysis for estimate of the water contact angle on a metallic Cu(111) surface, *Surfaces and Interfaces* 34 (2022) 102342. 765
766
52. A. Reznickova, V. Lacmanova, M. Hubalek Kalbacova, P. Hausild, J. Nohava, Z. Kolska, A. Kutova, P. Slepicka, As-deposited and dewetted Cu layers on plasma treated glass: adhesion study and its effect on biological response. *Appl. Surf. Sci. Adv.* 24 (2024) 100639. 767
768
769
53. S. M. Lößlein, R. Merz, Y. Rodríguez-Martínez, F. Schäfer, P. G. Grützmacher, D. Horwat, M. Kopnarski, F. Mücklich, Influence of chemistry and topography on the wettability of copper, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* 670 (2024) 658–675. 770
771
54. G. Grass, C. Rensing, M. Solioz, Metallic copper as an antimicrobial surface. *Appl. Environmental Microbiol.*, 77 (2011) 1541–1547. 772
773
55. M. Vincent, R. E. Duval, P. Hartemann, M. Engels-Deutsch, Contact killing and antimicrobial properties of copper. *J. Appl. Microbiology*, 124 (2018) 1032–1046. 774
775
56. J. A. Lemire, J. J., Harrison, R. J. Turner, Antimicrobial activity of metals: mechanisms, molecular targets and applications. *Nature Reviews Microbiol.*, 11 (2013) 371–384. 776
777
57. X. Ma, S. Zhou, X. Xu, Q. Du, Copper-containing nanoparticles: Mechanism of antimicrobial effect and application in dentistry—a narrative review, *Front. Surg.* 9 (2022) 905892. 778
779
780
781

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